

6GSNS

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6G-SANDBOX

White Paper

THIRD PARTY EXPERIMENTATION Engagement process and technical information

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1 PURPOSE AND FUNDAMENTAL STEPS

In alignment with the overall project objectives, the 6G-SANDBOX facility is open to other SNS Projects (Stream, A, B and D) as well as to external organizations, including industry, SMEs, research institutions, and academia. The 6G-SANDBOX is open to any interested party that targets performing experiments or bringing & validate new technologies, by using the 6G-SANDBOX infrastructure and tools.

- This openness refers to interactions where **no funding is provided by the project to third parties**. It is a separate activity, decoupled from the funding-based experimentation realized through the [open call activity](#) of the project.
- This openness targets the maximum engagement/synergy with other SNS projects as **it derives from the SNS JU projects collaboration agreement**. For stream A/B projects, the 6G-SANDBOX facility can be seen as an opportunity to validate their technologies; while for Stream D projects, the 6G-SANDBOX facility can be the underlay network for vertical use cases and KPI measurement campaigns.
- For **any third party** that want to interact (perform experiments or validate technologies) with the 6G-SANDBOX facility, the first step of the engagement process is to contact us by sending to experimenter@6g-sandbox.eu the **third-party contact form, available in the project website and also enclosed in this document in the ANNEX**
- The ecosystem that is created through the third party collaborations is depicted on our [website](#) (established-collaborations tab), providing the relevant **visibility to the involved third parties**.

Figure 1 below depicts the various paths available to third parties towards engaging with 6G-SANDBOX. This document focuses on the right branch of the figure, i.e., the non-funded program.

Figure 1: 6G-SANDBOX openness to other SNS projects and 3rd parties

2 EXPERIMENTATION POTENTIAL

6G-SANDBOX is a HE funded research project (HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-C-01-01). The project brings a complete and modular facility for the European experimentation ecosystem (in line and under the directions set by SNS JU), which is expected to provide support for the next decade for technology and research validation processes needed in the pathway towards 6G. In scope of the proposed facility are technologies and research advances, that span over the entire service provisioning chain, and refer to user/data, control and management planes.

From the experimentation perspective 6G-SANDBOX addresses two key challenges. The first challenge is that, so far, the experimenter does not have access to the internal configuration of the network components; for instance, to test new AI/ML algorithms for any optimization at the network or service level, a fine-tuning of the underlay communication and compute infrastructure is required by the infrastructure owner. The second challenge is the lack of capability to run medium- or long-term experiments, or even complete projects, without the need for time-consuming manual reconfiguration and provisioning of the setup from time to time. Both obstacles are related to the poor capability of the underlay infrastructure to automatically support pure automation and multi-tenancy in a secure way. By addressing these challenges, a more *industrialized (automated-repeatable)* way for 6G experimentation services is proposed in the 6G-SANDBOX project, with benefits for both the experimenters and experimentation platform providers.

In this context, 6G-SANDBOX provides the means for the generation of testbeds in the form of **Trial Networks**. A Trial Network (TN) is defined as a fully configurable, manageable, and controllable network that combines virtual, physical, and emulated resources to enable experiments for validating 6G technologies and measure 6G KPIs. Instances of Trial Networks might be offered targeting specific network domains and technologies, while within the 6G-SANDBOX project, end-to-end Trial Networks are offered by the four experimentation platforms (network and compute infrastructures) of the project.

The Trial Network software components are described in a common repository, called in the project framework as **6G Library**¹, which eases an experimenter to perform a modular and automatic deployment of a Trial Network by selecting on demand the required elements from the library.

The 6G library's objects are curated and designed to serve as the foundational building blocks for building the Trial Networks. For the library implementation Github serves as a sophisticated version control system essential for monitoring changes within computer files, primarily employed in managing source code during software development. Each element within the 6G library embodies the *Everything as a code - EaC*² philosophy, designed as self-contained unit equipped with the necessary automations and scripts for deployment within a 6G-SANDBOX platform (network and compute infrastructure)

At management level, to ensure uniformity across component creation and seamless integration, a set of predefined requirements and best practices has been established. The architectural blueprint of a component (6G library element) has been meticulously crafted with a focus on simplicity, clarity, versatility, scalability, and adaptability. In this view, every element in the library is becoming Trial Network-ready by complying with a specific predefined toolset (namely Terraform, Ansible, Jenkins, and Ansible) and is hosted under a common folder structure (see for more info [D3.1](#))

6G Library contains descriptors of software and hardware components, such as the Mobile Core, several RAN/ORAN options, UE devices, TSN infrastructure, Satellite backhaul, emulators, traffic generators, etc., that can be cherry-picked to compose a Trial Network and run experiments. All the tools needed for experimentation are also treated as Trial network components. At functional level, the 6G-SANDBOX project provides a **common API framework** for all the components of the 6G-library that need to interact at application level with third party software / experimenter.

The brain for the realization of the Trial Network Concept is the **Trial Network Life-Cycle Manager** (TNLCM). The TNLCM is, within the 6G-SANDBOX Architecture, the entity that ensures that every Trial Network in each platform is accessible and in working order, as well as orchestrates the necessary actions required for changing the state of a Trial Network

¹ <https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library>

² Eac involves utilizing code to define and manage IT resources, encompassing principles such as Infrastructure as Code and Config as Code.

when necessary (see [D4.1](#)). A Trial Network is made up of several components of the 6G Library; the TNLCM is the orchestrator in charge of deploying each of the components and managing the life cycle of the Trial Network itself.

The Trial Networks are offered to third parties through four experimentation **platforms** distributed in EU (namely the [Athens](#), [Berlin](#), [Malaga](#), and [Oulu](#) platforms). Those platforms bring the required network and compute infrastructure for the Trial Networks as described in [Section 4](#) as well as a rich and extensible **testing and validation toolbox** as provided in [Section 5](#)

A third party that wants to interact with the 6G-SANDBOX facility could have one or more of the predefined roles as presented in the [Section 3](#) of this document.

Figure 2: Abstract representation of the experimentation approach on Trial Networks.

An abstract representation of the experimentation approach with Trial Networks is depicted in Figure 2. The basic step /prerequisite (offline process conducted by the 6G-SANDBOX partners) is the enrichment of the 6G-library with software components as well as representation models of the physical components that reside at the four 6G-SANDBOX platforms. In this step the TNLCM is becoming aware of the platform capabilities and the resource availability for each 6G-SANDBOX platform. Third parties may use the TN portal to set up a TN (step 2 in Figure 2), and then they use the experimentation manager that they have selected as part of their TN to run an experiment (step 3 in Figure 2). The default experimentation manager offered is the 6G-SANDBOX Experimentation Lifecycle Manager ([ELCM](#)). The use of other experimentation managers is not excluded (for instance the use of Pathwave test automation cloud/ KS8500 by keysight).

Meant to create tangible and long-term impact, the **6G KPIs and KVIs** that will be quantified with the facility during the experiment, will be released to any interested party; while the set of developments and APIs that will be produced, will feed an **open repository** as an initial step to move the contributions and the lessons learned beyond the project borders. This repository is depicted in Figure 2 as *6G KPI and KVI open repository*. In [Section 6.2](#) we provide some guidelines on how application level KPIs can be pushed to this repository.

3 THIRD PARTY ROLES IN 6G-SANDBOX

In this section the main roles that a third party can play to the 6G-SANDBOX facility are defined, indicating the access level provided, the integration activity required as well as the services that the 6G-SANDBOX provides.

Table 1: Third Party Roles in 6G-SANDBOX, profile, access levels, and services provided

Role	Profile	Access level	Integration Required	Services offered by 6G-SANDBOX
6G-SANDBOX Trial Network User (TNU)	Someone that creates test cases (or uses the available ones) and conducts measurement campaigns. The TNU can also bring an application, deploy it, and link it (through API interaction) to a Trial Network that is selected and activated for the experiment.	The TNU has access to the portals used for experiments conduction, and the TNU software has secure API interaction to every component that is part of the selected Trial Network and provides API services through CAPIF.	(Optional) A containerised application or an (IP) network node provided by the TNU.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whatever provided through the Experimenters Portal • TN selection. • Test case composition. • Third party application deployment. • Support on using the APIs provided by the TN selected. • Results collection and analysis.
6G-SANDBOX Trial Network Operator/Owner (TNO)	Someone that creates a Trial Network from the components that the 6G-SANDBOX facility provides (i.e., the 6G-Library and the technologies physically integrated in the 6G-SANDBOX Platforms). The TNO can also play the role of a TNU or allow other TNUs to conduct experiment to the Trial Network created.	The access level of a TNU plus i) admin rights to configure a specific portion of computational resources where the TN is set / hosted and ii) remote access to platform specific physical or virtual components to set the Trial Network.	Provisioning of computational resources as well as configurations for the TN components and/or addition of components to the 6G-Library.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TN establishment. • TN exploitation for experiments conducted either by the TNO itself or by third parties. • Test cases composition. • Third party application deployment. • Support on using the APIs provided by the TN created. • Results collection and analysis.
Third party Technology Provider for the 6G-SANDBOX facility	Someone that brings 6G component(s) or software solutions and is willing to integrate them with one or more Platforms for expanding the 6G-SANDBOX capabilities.	Access to platform specific physical or virtual components and interfaces needed to integrate a specific SW/HW component	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SW/HW components that incorporate 6G technologies or services that are integrated and become part of the 6G-SANDBOX facility (the integrated components remain for further by the project or third parties). • CAPIF compliant APIs should be offered if interaction/ configuration is needed when the component is part of an experiment. 	On-demand and Platform-oriented support services related to the integration process and the component validation tests.
Third party host for the 6G-SANDBOX framework	An owner of an end-to-end experimentation platform / testbed who is interested in adopting 6G-SANDBOX framework (i.e., the concept of creating TNs on top of the testbed)	Access to an instance of the software package that has been developed in the project to support of the TNs concept.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An end-to-end 5G/6G testbed with a Kubernetes or similar cluster available. • CAPIF compliant APIs should be offered for the interaction/configuration of the testbed components from the 6G-SANDBOX framework. 	Documentation and assistance on getting and using the 6G-SANDBOX Toolkit ³ .

³ <https://6g-sandbox.eu/6g-sandbox-toolkit/>

3.1 TRIAL NETWORK USER

The role of Trial Network User (TNU) can be played by someone that creates test cases (or uses the available ones) and conducts measurement campaigns. The TNU can also bring an application, deploy it, and link it (through API interaction) to a Trial Network that is selected and activated for the experiment. A TNU has access to the portals used for experiments conduction, while the TNU software has secure API interaction to every component that is part of the selected Trial Network and provides API services through CAPIF (see [Section 5.3](#)).

Figure 3: Trial Network user representation of the interaction with 6G-SANDBOX facility

3.2 TRIAL NETWORK OWNER/OPERATOR

The role of Trial Network Operator (TNO) can be played by someone that creates a Trial Network from the components that the 6G-SANDBOX facility provides (i.e., the 6G-Library and the technologies physically integrated in the 6G-SANDBOX Platforms). The TNO can also play the role of a TNU or allow other TNUs to conduct experiments to the Trial Network created. The access level provided to a TNO is the one provide to a TNU plus i) admin rights to configure a specific portion of computational resources where the TN is set / hosted and ii) remote access to platform specific physical or virtual components to set the Trial Network.

Figure 4: Trial Network Owner/Operator – representation of the interaction with the 6G-SANDBOX facility

3.3 6G-SANDBOX 3RD PARTY TECHNOLOGY PROVIDER

The role of a 3rd Party Technology Provider can be played by someone that brings 6G component(s) or software solutions and is willing to integrate them with one or more Platforms for expanding the 6G-SANDBOX capabilities. A 3rd Party Technology Provider has access to platform specific physical or virtual components and interfaces needed to integrate a specific SW/HW component.

Figure 5: 3rd Party Technology provider – representation of the interaction with the 6G-SANDBOX facility

3.4 6G-SANDBOX 3RD PARTY PLATFORM OWNER/OPERATOR

This role is for the owner/operator of an end-to-end experimentation platform/testbed who is interested in adopting 6G-SANDBOX framework (i.e., the concept of creating TNs on top of the testbed). The 3rd Party Platform Owner utilizes an instance of the **6G-SANDBOX Toolkit**⁴ that has been developed in the project to support the TNs concept.

Figure 6: 3rd Party Platform Owner/Operator – representation of the interaction with the 6G-SANDBOX facility

⁴ <https://6g-sandbox.eu/6g-sandbox-toolkit/>

4 THE 6G-SANDBOX PLATFORMS

This section summarizes the network and compute components of the 6G-SANDBOX platforms and provides a topological view of their infrastructure.

Table 2: Main network and compute components available in the 6G-SANDBOX platforms

HW/SW	Description	Identifier	Berlin	Athens	Malaga	Oulu
Radio Access Domain						
HW	5G Radio + Baseband	Nokia Airscale	X		X	X
HW	5G Radio + Baseband	Nokia Airscale , Huawei	X			
HW	5G Radio + Baseband	Amarisoft Classic		X		
HW	5G Radio + Baseband	Ericsson		X		
HW	Software Defined Radio	B210	X			X
HW	Software Defined Radio	N310			X	X
HW	5G Indoor Pico	N/A			X	X
SW	OAIBOX Full 5G with USRP	N/A				X
HW	RU	Benetel RAN650, Benetel RAN550	X		X	
SW	DU + CU	IS-Wireless solutions			X	
HW	Radio Access Domain	QUB-RIS solutions			X	
SW	gNodeB + UE Simulator	UERANSIM	X	X	X	
Network Core						
SW	Full 5G Core	Open5GS	X	X	X	X
HW/SW	Full 5G Core	Amarisoft Classic	X	X		
SW	Full 5G Core	free5GC		X		
SW	Full 5G Core	Open5GCore	X			
SW	Full 5G Core	ATHONET 5GC		X		
SW	Full 5G Core	Polaris 5GC			X	
SW	LMF	LMF		X		
SW	NWDAF	NWDAF		X		
SW	NEF	NEF Emulator		X		
HW/SW	Stand Alone UPF	UPF from Open5GS, P4-UPF		X	X	
HW/SW	Stand Alone UPF	ATHONET UPF		X		
Compute infrastructure						
SW	Server manager to create VMs, Containers, etc	Open Nebula, XXX	X	X	X	
SW	KVM Virtual Machine	KVM Virtualization	X		X	
SW	Virtual Networks, VLAN, VXLAN, ...	Open Nebula	X	X	X	
SW	Kubernetes Cluster solution compatible with vanilla K8s	ONEKE			X	

HW	GPU Cards with PCI bus	Nvidia RX2070 Super				
HW	GPU Cards with PCI bus	Nvidia A10		X		
HW	GPU Cards with PCI bus	Nvidia RTX4080, Nvidia T4			X	
HW	Accelerators cards with PCI Bus	FPGAs, SmartNICs, ...				
SW	NFVI performance testing	CloudPeak		X	X	
SW	Cloud scalability and security	Cyperf		X	X	
SW	Kubernetes Cluster solution compatible with vanilla K8s	ICTF				X
SW	VMware Virtual Machine	ICTF				X
Transport Network						
HW	Datacenter Switches to connect RAN, Servers, etc	Mellanox		X		
HW	Datacenter Switches to connect RAN, Servers, etc	Mikrotic, CISCO Nexus, HP Aruba/Flexfabric	X	X		
HW	Datacenter switches to connect, RAN, Servers, etc	Netgear, P4 switches			X	
HW	TSN endpoints and bridge	N/A			X	
SW	Firewall/Bastion to provide access to Trial Network through VPN	PFSense		X	X	
SW	NTP service for Time synchronization	OpenNTPD			X	
SW	DNS service for Trial Networks	BIND			X	
HW/SW	Satellite Backhaul for the testbed	Starlink	X	X	X	
SW	end-to-end satellite communication system	OpenSAND		X		
SW	Multipath protocol	N/A			X	
SW	Firewall FortiNet Fortigate	N/A				X

4.1 TOPOLOGICAL VIEW OF TECHNOLOGIES AND COMPONENTS PER PLATFORM

In the following subsections the components listed in Table 2 are provided in a topological view per platform while a color code is used to highlight the baseline deployments (Green boxes) the recent deployments (orange boxes) as well as the associated deployments – conducted in the framework of other projects (purple boxes).

The Berlin platform

Figure 7: The Berlin Platform

The Athens platform

Figure 8: Athens Platform

The Malaga platform

Figure 9: Malaga Platform

The Oulu platform

Figure 10: Oulu Platform

5 TESTING AND VALIDATION TOOLBOX

All pertinent 6G test and measurement software tools provided by Keysight are available for deployment and use in the 6G-SANDBOX platforms. The full list of the available tools (with an indication to the platform that they can be used) is provided in the Table below. In addition, the key characteristics and capabilities of each tool are presented in the subsections that follow. **A representative list of the KPIs** that can be measured is provided in the [ANNEX](#).

Table 3: Testing and validation toolbox available in the 6G-SANDBOX platforms

HW/SW	Description	Identifier	Berlin	Athens	Malaga	Oulu
Testing and validation tools						
SW	Performance and Cybersecurity Testing	Breakingpoint		X	X	
SW	Virtual network infrastructure validation	Cloudpeak		X	X	
SW	Scalable network application and security testing for distributed cloud	CyPerf		X	X	
SW	Active network performance monitoring (QoS monitoring, application & web monitoring, Wi-Fi monitoring, cloud monitoring)	HawKeye		X	X	
HW/SW	5G Wireless Test Platform	UXM			X	
SW	L4-7 performance testing and QoE testing	IxLoad		X	X	
SW	L2-3 network infrastructure performance testing	IxNetwork		X	X	
SW	5G Core Testing and Validation	LoadCore	X	X	X	X
SW	Breach and attack simulation platform	ThreatSimulator			X	
SW	Network Digital Twin	EXATA	X	X	X	X
HW/SW	Emulation of O-RAN network nodes and traffic profiles on different RAN Intelligent Controller's (RIC's) interfaces	RIC test			X	
HW/SW	O-RAN Radio Unit (O-RU) Testing and Validation	O-RAN studio			X	
SW	Radio Access Network Testing	UeSIM			X	
SW	O-RAN Midhaul solution	CuSIM			X	
SW	O-RAN Fronthaul solution	RuSIM			X	

5.1 BREAKINGPOINT

Performance and Cybersecurity Testing

Capabilities: web, encrypted-web, data center, social-media, and business application mix tests, application protocols

Highlights:

- Simulates more than 640 real-world application protocols
- Allows for customization and manipulation of any protocol, including raw data
- Generates a mix of protocols at high speed with realistic protocol weight
- Offers HTTP1.0, HTTP1.1 and HTTP/2 as transport with support for NAT and Proxy (for selected applications)
- Supports more than 110,000 attacks and malwares
- Delivers from a single port all types of traffic simultaneously, including legitimate traffic, DDoS, and malware
- Bi-monthly Application and Threat Intelligence (ATI) subscription updates ensure you are current with the latest applications and threats
- Combined with the CloudStorm platform, BreakingPoint reaches a staggering performance with a fully-populated chassis—2.4 Tbps / 1.44 billion sessions and 42 million connections per second—to emulate enterprise-wide networks to continent scale mobile carrier networks
- Leverages the hyperscale performance of the new APS-100/400GE Series platform. A single APS-ONE-100 delivers unparalleled real-world TLS performance of up to 100K TLS connections per second and 3.2M TLS concurrent connections and 150Gbps encrypted throughput. The ground-breaking scale of a 10-appliance system generates 1M TLS CPS, 32M TLS concurrent connections, and 1.5 Tbps encrypted TLS throughput.

5.2 CLOUDPEAK

Virtual network infrastructure validation

Capabilities: web application to benchmark the performance of virtualized network infrastructures, Network Functions Virtualization (NFV), NFV Infrastructure (NFVI), management and orchestration (MANO), mobile edge computing (MEC)

Highlights:

- Validate and benchmark VMware vCenter and OpenStack-based private clouds
- Testbed for single compute node or large environments with many racks
- Individually validate the compute / network / storage performance dimensions
- Measure VIM performance with custom VM instantiation / VM termination test methodology
- Leverage subscription licensing for low startup cost and flexibility of pay-as-you-grow model
- Predefined test scenarios for NFVI validation
- Validate from a VNF or network perspective through real workload and powerful traffic emulation
- Includes industry-proven workload emulation from the OPNFV Yardstick portfolio
- Measure scheduler capability to isolate the good workloads and the bad noisy neighbors
- Measure the performance impact of VNF instantiation and VNF workloads in presence of (noisy) neighbors

5.3 CYPERF

Scalable network application and security testing for distributed cloud

Capabilities:

CyPerf employs lightweight agents deployed across a variety of environments to realistically model dynamic application traffic, user behavior, and threat vectors at scale. It validates cloud and hybrid networks, security devices, zero trust implementations and services for more confident rollouts.

CyPerf generates authenticated and unauthenticated application traffic and security attacks across a complex network of proxies, software-defined wide area networking (SD-WAN), Secure Access Service Edge (SASE), SSL VPN tunnels, IPsec tunnels, Transport Layer Security (TLS) inspection, elastic load balancers, web applications firewalls (WAF) and zero trust enabled environments.

Highlights:

- Test the functionality and performance of zero trust policies with authenticated and unauthenticated application traffic and security attacks.

- Validate cloud, SASE, and SD-WAN migration in half the time with more fidelity by replicating distributed deployment environments with realistic workloads.
- Emulate thousands of SSL VPN tunnels to test the scale, performance, and robustness of VPN Gateways.
- Validate the control plane performance and scalability of IPsec Gateways, as well as the application performance and security efficacy of IPsec VPN enabled network security solutions.
- Perform head-to-head comparisons to determine the most cost-effective cloud infrastructure and security controls.
- Validate elastic scalability of cloud infrastructures and security architectures with dynamic auto-scaling test agents.
- Access key performance indicators easily—application throughput, max concurrency (connections / users), application latency, Transport Layer Security (TLS) performance, and threat detection efficacy.
- Measure and compare hybrid, multi-cloud, container infrastructures for your specific workloads and security controls.

5.4 HAWKEYE

Active network performance monitoring (QoS monitoring, application & web monitoring, Wi-Fi monitoring, cloud monitoring)

Highlights:

- Take control of user experience with real-time QoS monitoring
- Proactively detect, diagnose, and fix performance problems
- Validate deployments by simulating live network traffic
- Monitor distributed networks from core to edge
- Troubleshoot outages faster with hop-by-hop visualization

Hawkeye supports a variety of service level agreement (SLA) and quality of experience (QoE) objectives, including:

- Speed test from site to site with advanced configuration on traffic profiling
- Advanced Bandwidth availability or verification with bit blasting or TCP-based testing
- Class of service (COS) implementation validation with oversubscription scenarios
- IP network SLA verification (one-way delay, jitter, loss)
- Unified communications tests (Teams, Zoom)
- Office 365 applications
- Real-time streaming verification
 - o Mean opinion score (MOS) for voice – G711, G729, AMR ...
 - o Media delivery index (MDI) for video streaming
- Echo tests (ICMP, TCP, UDP) and path discovery to any interface on the web
- User experience tests (downloading web pages, etc.)
- DNS response time
- Netflix, YouTube, and any Dash/Adaptive streaming test
- Multicast video
- Remote destination port opening verification
- Wi-Fi monitoring

Deployment solution:

- Deploy Hawkeye on premise web server in central location (NOC, data center, etc.)
- Deploy software and hardware endpoints to any network location:
 - Customer premises
 - Mobile devices – Wi-Fi or Cellular
 - Remote sites and head offices
 - Network aggregation points (PEs)
 - Core network, MPLS routers
 - Data centers
 - Virtual machines and servers
- In public cloud locations (Amazon, Azure...)

5.5 UXM 5G WIRELESS TEST PLATFORM (MALAGA CENTERED)

Highlights:

The Keysight E7515B UXM 5G wireless test solution is a highly integrated signaling test platform with multiformat stack support, rich processing power, and abundant RF resources. Supporting the latest 3GPP Release 15 and beyond, the E7515B UXM 5G wireless test solution enables you to establish a 5G call with a device under test (DUT) in different 5G New Radio (NR) deployment modes; non-stand-alone (NSA), stand-alone (SA), and frequency bands FR1 and FR2. The solution performs signaling test for device RF characteristics, protocol compliance, and functional key performance indicators. It also supports LTE, eMTC and C-V2X signaling formats.

The E7515B UXM 5G wireless test solution supports extended test coverage in a single unit, including the following capabilities:

- 5G NR 8CC DL, 4 CC UL 2x2, with LTE 2CC
- Wide bandwidth in each RF port
- Multiple angle of arrival (AoA) test
- Internal fading for 5G NR and LTE formats
- Frequency extensions to high IF and millimeter-wave with the use of a common interface unit and remote radio heads (RRH)

5.6 IXLOAD

L4-7 performance testing and QoE testing by emulating web, video, voice, storage, VPN, wireless, infrastructure, and encapsulation/security protocols to create realistic scenarios.

Highlights:

- Offers the industry's highest HTTP, SSL, and IPsec performance and scale
- Delivers end-to-end testing of converged wireless and wired application delivery infrastructure and services
- Provides real-time insight into QoE
- Emulates fully integrated broadband network infrastructures with application traffic testing
- Serves as the only test solution in the market that can model the dynamic nature of user behavior
- Achieves seamless application performance validation across physical and virtual networks

Featured test:

- IxLoad Wireless Evolved Packet Core Simulation
- IxLoad Wireless eNodeB Simulation
- IxLoad Wi-Fi Offload
- IxLoad Data Test Solution
- IxLoad Video Test Solution
- IxLoad Voice Test Solution

5.7 IXNETWORK

L2-3 network infrastructure performance testing.

Highlights:

- Offers test coverage from 1G to 800G Ethernet
- Provides comprehensive protocol coverage for routing/switching, multiprotocol label switching (MPLS), software-defined networking (SDN), data center networking, carrier Ethernet, broadband access, time synchronization, automotive and industrial Ethernet (AVB/TSN), L2 security (MACsec)
- Generates traffic flows that mimic realistic user applications and scenarios
- Works smoothly in virtualized network environments, and runs from any commercially available compute environment
- Delivers end-to-end test system automation
- Performs rapid isolation of service violations, including thorough traffic-flow analysis

5.8 LOADCORE

5G Core Testing and Validation

Highlights:

- Simulate UE behavior in 5G use case deployments: Network slicing, multi-access edge computing (MEC) low latency and offloading, video optimization
- Perform service quality validation with subscriber modeling, multiplay traffic generation, and quality of experience (QoE) measurements
- Validate complex scenarios for service-based architectures
- Validate 5G nodes and interfaces via specialized Ixia hardware or Virtual Edition (VE)
- Scale up to millions of subscribers using stateful application traffic mixes that can interact with real servers and peers
- Enforce and validate multiple user-plane QoS characteristics per flow or session
- Control test traffic mix and intensity using network objectives to independently manage control- and user-planes

5.9 THREATSIMULATOR

A breach and attack simulation platform that provides enterprise security teams with insights into the effectiveness of their security posture and actionable intelligence to improve it.

Highlights:

- Part of Keysight's Security Operations Suite of enterprise security tools.
- Safe and cost-effective way to measure and validate the effectiveness of your production security tools.
- Enables you to perform automated breach and attack simulations on a regular basis.
- Eliminates the assumptions that security controls are deployed and configured correctly.
- Identify environmental drifts from historical visualized results.
- Active validation of all phases of the Attack Life Cycle.
- Reduces compliance audit time with data-driven evidence.
- Prove security attacks are properly identified and reported.
- Justify current and future IT spending.
- Content refreshed at regular intervals, including the provision of malware feeds daily.

5.10 EXATA

Network Digital Twins — Development, analysis, testing and cyber assessment.

Highlights:

- Scalability to thousands of nodes enables more sophisticated design and analysis
- Real-time simulation optimizes productivity
- High-fidelity models deliver accurate results
- Cost-effective "lab-based risk reduction" network simulation technology provides solutions to mission-critical, business-critical problems
- Test and validate interoperability, scalability, and performance: Seamless integration with live equipment such as servers, computers, radios, and sensors as well as a full network environment
- Accurately analyze behavior under different network conditions: Integrate with live applications such as VoIP, chat, video feeds, file transfers, and database queries
- Analyze and capture network traffic with packet sniffer/analysis tools
- Interaction with Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP) managers from companies such as Hewlett-Packard, IBM, and SolarWinds

5.11 CLOUDLENS

Public, Private, Hybrid Cloud Visibility

Highlights:

- Capture and forward Full Packets and/or Netflow from Virtual Machine (VM), containers or inter-Pod network traffic and forward it to tools, or physical and/or virtual packet brokers for aggregation, advanced filtering, and deduplication
- Virtual packet processing and aggregation in your cloud which traditionally relies on packet brokers
- Aggregate and deduplicate packet data; originate and terminate tunnels without the need for hardware
- Virtual packet processing with AppStack capabilities leverages Keysight's advanced application intelligence with signature-based application detection, geolocation, NetFlow and IxFlow (enhanced NetFlow)
- Management UI that can be deployed in any cloud, for better control and security
- Multi-platform capable, cloud service provider and platform agnostic
- Auto-scales elastically, on-demand with cloud instances
- Handles cloud scale (thousands of instances). Auto-scales elastically, on-demand with cloud instances
- Easy-to-use, drag-and-drop interface with a network to tools layout

5.12 PATHWAVE SYSTEM DESIGN (SYSTEMVUE)

One environment for system architecture, design, and verification

Highlights:

High fidelity RF characterization built in

1. Non-linearity, spurs, phase noise, impedance, and more
2. X-parameters, fast circuit envelope models
3. Verified waveforms and vector modulation analysis
4. Shared measurement science with decades of Keysight instrumentation designs
5. Flows directly into chip- and circuit-level RF design

Multi-domain modeling and simulation

6. Everything needed for physical layer (layer 1) analysis
7. Behavioral model libraries in intuitive workflow
8. Simulation in both time- and frequency-domain
9. Open interfaces for third party RF component models

Phased array analysis

10. Powerful frequency, time, and cross-domain simulation of complete phased array systems
11. 'Best in class' simulation speed for phased arrays and other complex RF designs
12. Intuitive array configuration and links to antenna design software
13. Beam measurement and visualization tools
14. 5G, Radar, EW, and Satellite applications

Libraries for real-world RF systems

15. MilCom & SatCom data links and SDR
16. Electronic warfare, SIGINT, and EMSO
17. Space vehicle communication links
18. 5G NR and 3GPP specifications
19. Wi-Fi 6 and connectivity specifications
20. Automotive radar systems

5.13 RIC TEST (MALAGA CENTERED)

RIC Test emulates O-RAN network nodes and traffic profiles on different RAN Intelligent Controller's (RIC's) interfaces, allowing testing of the Near Real-Time RIC (and of xApps it hosts) and of the Non-Real-Time RIC (and of rApps it hosts).

Highlights:

- Supports all E2 node types defined in the standard, at configurable mix and quantity
- Supports 5G NSA and SA configurations
- Simulation of thousands of sessions across multiple emulated E2 nodes

- Configurable allocation of emulated (UE ranges to each node
- Configurable traffic modeling to drive measurements of interest towards the xApp
- E2AP and E2 interface support
- O1 interface support
- Stateful E2AP for each emulated node
- Key performance measurements (KPM) service model support for all node types
- Network interface (NI) and RAN control (RC) service models support in roadmap

5.14 WAVEJUDGE WIRELESS ANALYZER

Modular and scalable test platform that captures and decodes LTE, 5G, and Wi-Fi signals as a part of the SJ001A WaveJudge Wireless Analyzer Toolset

Highlights:

- Unique solution for passive signal capture and analysis
- Support for 5G real time decoding
- Support for 3GPP NR Rel 15-17 (NR NTN, RedCap, V2X)
- Support for 3GPP LTE Rel 9-16
- Support for Wi-Fi 802.11ax and 802.11be
- Channel BW up to 800 MHz per port
- RF ports scalable chassis, 2, 4, 6, or 8
- Single RF module covering FR1 and FR2 bands
- SSD storage for long IQ captures to troubleshoot intermittent issues
- Superior EVM and decoding performance
- Streaming analytics and charting
- Advanced triggers
- Expanded filtering and visualizations

5.15 UESIM UE EMULATION SOLUTIONS (MALAGA CENTERED)

For Radio Access Network Testing

Highlights:

- 5G RAN functionality validation (NSA/SA mode) by full protocol stack assessment, from layer 1 to 7
- Functional testing – full stack and single layer – up to thousands of UEs
- Load testing of 5G RAN
- Up to 8xCC, 2x2/4x4 MIMO, 256 QAM DL/UL
- FR1, FR2, O-RAN eCPRI
- Massive MIMO AAS, MU-MIMO support
- Extremely compact footprint with potential to grow up to 5,000 active UEs/cell
- gNB wrap-around testing with core emulation option
- O-RAN fronthaul interface support with different 5G RAN split architecture options
- Real smartphones applications and traffic profiles simulation
- Service quality validation with subscriber modeling, and multi-play voice, video, and data traffic generation: eMBMS, VoNR/VoLTE, ViNR/ViLTE
- Inter-Beam and Inter-Cell advanced mobility scenarios support
- Fading and interference simulation
- OTA/field and conducted/lab testing
- 3GPP R15/R16 support

5.16 CU SIM – O-DU MIDHAUL SOLUTIONS (MALAGA CENTERED)

CuSIM helps infrastructure vendors, chipset providers and mobile operators active in the O-RAN arena to validate the O-DU functionality by emulating traffic over the midhaul interface

Highlights:

1. Cloud Native Architecture
2. Support of Standalone configuration procedures
3. Support of thousands of sessions across multiple O-DUs
4. Non-UE Associated F1-AP Signaling
5. UE-associated F1-AP Procedures
6. RRC and NAS Procedures
7. Support for DU Handovers
8. Network Initiated and UE Initiated QoS flows
9. VoNR
10. Option to configure single or multiple PDU sessions per UE
11. Topology-driven User Interface

5.17 RuSIM — UE/O-RU EMULATION OVER THE O-RAN FRONTHAUL

RuSIM enables infrastructure vendors, chipset providers and mobile operators to validate end-to-end Radio Access Network performance by emulating real network traffic over the O-RAN fronthaul interface.

Highlights:

1. Functional testing — layer by layer — up to thousands of emulated UEs
2. Performance and load testing
3. Protocol conformance testing
4. Compliance testing against interoperability specifications
5. Core emulation option for wrap-around testing
6. Fully scalable solution
7. Service quality validation with realistic subscriber and traffic modeling at a high scale

5.18 N6705C DC POWER ANALYZER

The N6705C DC Power Analyzer provides unrivaled productivity gains for sourcing and measuring DC voltage and current into the DUT.

Highlights:

- Ammeter accuracy: Up to 0.025% + 8 nA; up to 18 bits
- Arbitrary waveform generator function: Bandwidth up to 100 kHz, output power up to 500 W
- Data logger function: Measurement interval from 20 μ s to 60 seconds, with a maximum of 500 M readings per second
- Scope function: Digitizes voltage and current up to 200 kHz, 512 kpts; up to 18 bits
- Voltmeter accuracy: Up to 0.025% + 50 μ V; up to 18 bits

5.19 O-RAN STUDIO

for O-RAN Radio Unit (O-RU) Testing and Validation

Highlights:

- Quickly configure and generate 5G NR and LTE 3GPP single or multi-carrier compliant FDD and TDD waveforms
- Fully automated generation of Ethernet based O-RAN CU-plane messages with eCPRI transport encapsulation types compliant with ORAN-WG4.CUS.0-v10.00
- Real-time FrameID generation and CRC Calculation
- Analyze both FR1 and FR2 radio downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) paths
- O-RAN Sections types and Section Extensions configuration
- Beamforming support
- Capture and accurately timestamp O-RAN responses
- Visualize and fully decode O-RAN traces with flow-based filtering

- Supports split option 7.2x compliant CU-plane stimulus generation and analysis
- Measure O-RAN traffic over 10 Gbps / 25 Gbps (fronthaul) Ethernet interfaces

5.20 AC POWER ANALYZER

The Keysight IntegraVision power analyzer is an intuitive combination of accurate power measurements and touch-driven oscilloscope visualization. Within a single instrument, it delivers the dynamic views you need to see, measure, and prove the performance of your design.

Highlights:

- Measure voltage, current, and power on 4 channels: DC, 1-phase AC or 3-phase AC
- Make more accurate power measurements: 0.05% at 50/60 Hz
- Measure current directly: internal shunts to 50 Arms, or with external probes or transducers
- Address multiple test scenarios with isolated inputs
- Achieve power analyzer accuracies and scope-like waveform visualization with reduced setup time
- Address multiple test scenarios with the flexibility of wide-ranging, isolated inputs
- Visualize transients, in-rush currents, and state changes with a high-speed digitizer that captures voltage, current, and power in real-time
- Analyze voltage, current, and power in the time and frequency domains
- Explore your design and gain new insights through the 12.1" / 310 mm high-resolution display with a touch interface
- Save space on your bench with a minimum-depth form factor.

5.21 NEMO WIRELESS

Nemo Wireless Network Solutions provides drive testing and analytics solutions for all stages of the wireless network life cycle from rollout to optimization and monitoring, both outdoors and indoors.

Highlights:

Nemo Handy

- Create complex measurement scripts more easily and effectively
- Reduce test time with the intuitive user interface
- Verify the end-user QoE (Quality of Experience) with a wide range of data-testing capabilities:
 - voice call testing, voice quality testing, FTP and HTTP data transfer testing, HTML browsing, email testing, iPerf testing, TWAMP testing, ping testing, SMS & MMS messaging testing, external application launch testing, mScore testing, Fast.com data testing, and video quality testing
 - social media testing apps/protocols, including YouTube video and live video streaming, Facebook testing, Twitter testing, LinkedIn testing, Instagram testing, Dropbox testing, Google Drive testing, WhatsApp testing, Line testing, BiP Messenger testing, Viber testing, and Zalo testing
- Navigation application providing turn-by-turn instructions for your drive test campaigns (optional)
- Perform large-scale site acceptance projects with the optional Nemo Handy Site Acceptance Edition together with Nemo Cloud
- Perform audio quality tests (POLQA versions 2 and 3) and video quality testing including 4K PEVQ-S
- Combine scanning and indoor measurements with portable, battery-operated PCTEL Gflex™ / IBflex™ / HBflex™ and R&S®TSMA6 Autonomous Mobile Network scanners
- Streamline operations and improve responsiveness with the Nemo Cloud option, a cloud-based platform for centralized remote control
- Create fast and efficient reports in the field with the optional Nemo Instant Report option
- Available in the following product editions: Nemo Handy Field Test (FT), Nemo Handy Basic, Nemo Handy Pro, Nemo Handy Pro+, Nemo Handy Lite, Nemo Handy Autonomous, Nemo Handy Work Order, Nemo Handy Site Acceptance, and Nemo Handy SSV (Single Site Verification)

Nemo Outdoor 5G NR Drive Test

- Quality-of-experience (QoE) metrics for the services and applications your customers are actually using.
- Automated measurements with extensive scripts and large-scale measurement lists enable you to focus on the actual task at hand during drive testing.
- User-defined parameters from signaling messages can be searched and displayed in info view and graph side panel during measurement and playback.
- Versatile benchmarking capabilities, including Nemo Network Benchmarking Solution (NBM) and Nemo Backpack Pro.
- Supports Qualcomm X50/X55/X60/X65/X70, Samsung Exynos 5100/5123/5123A/5123B/ 5133/5300, HiSilicon Balong 5000, and MediaTek M70/M80 modem-based devices, and 3rd party scanning receivers.
- Supports 5G NR standalone (SA) and non-standalone (NSA) mode testing.
- Supports 5G NR carrier aggregation testing.
- Supports 5G NR NSA/SA forcing.
- Supports 5G NR channel/PCI forcing.
- Collects 5G NR beam specific KPIs.
- Supports massive MIMO (mMIMO) drive tests and field measurements.
- Supports Dynamic Spectrum Sharing (DSS) measurements.

5.22 VXG SIGNAL GENERATORS

The Keysight M9383B VXG-m Microwave Signal Generator is the industry's first dual-channel microwave signal generator providing up to 44 GHz frequency.

Highlights:

- Wide RF bandwidth (2 GHz)
- High output power to compensate for system loss and enable 5G power amplifier and over-the-air (OTA) testing
- Phase coherent local oscillator (LO) and baseband synchronization for multiuser or beamforming MIMO OTA testing
- PathWave Signal Generation software supports application-specific and custom signal creation
- 3GPP 5G NR standard-compliant signals with channel coding and multi-antenna port support

6 TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR THIRD PARTIES

This section covers guidelines for the proposers to ensure specificities of the 6G-SANDBOX facility. These details are not expected to be part of the initial proposal, but proposers will be assisted to produce their final contributions considering all of them.

6.1 REQUIREMENTS FOR DEPLOYMENT IN VIRTUALIZED ENVIRONMENT

Proposers should provide enough information on the packages to deploy their software in the virtualized infrastructure available on each platform. The following information is a reference for software packages to be deployed in Open Nebula.

6.1.1 USING YOUR VIRTUAL MACHINES

An experimenter can prepare their own virtual machines to be part of the experiment:

- 6G-SANDBOX will provide **base templates** consisting of a base installation of popular operating systems. Initially Ubuntu, Debian, Alma Linux and FreeBSD will be provided.
- **Customized versions of the base templates** can be developed by the experimenter through the 6G-SANDBOX platform. The customized versions will be included in the 6G-SANDBOX for later use in any experimenter's TN.
- The experimenter can also customize the following attributes of the VM:
 - o **CPU topology**, including number of NUMA nodes, cores and threads per core
 - o **Memory**.
 - o **QoS requirements**, for example to ensure that a predictable number of resources are devoted to the VM.
 - o **Scratch storage** disks, to store experiment data during the experiment
 - o **User data**, to pass custom data to the VM (e.g., parameterization parameters or credentials) or execute custom scripts at boot time.
 - o **GPU**, devices to perform specific processing.

6.1.2 USING YOUR HELM CHARTS

When a Kubernetes cluster is deployed as part of the TN, the experimenter can include any application to be deployed automatically. The requirement to deploy such applications are:

- The Kubernetes application must be described as a helm chart
- The helm charts must be included in a repository provided by the experimenter
- All components referred by the helm chart need to be provided by the experimenter or accessible through a public repository.

6.1.3 PROPRIETARY SOFTWARE

6G-SANDBOX will not provide commercial software or specific OS aside from the one mentioned in this document. If your work requires a special version or specific operating system, please check for availability. If not available, be sure to plan for this as part of your work.

6.2 REQUIREMENTS FOR APPLICATION LEVEL KPIS

The collection and delivery of KPIs can be managed using *Network as Code* (NaC) paradigm using an Application Developer NaC API. This interface will provide a set of applicable functions that will be used by the end-device connected application. The functions will provide information about the application KPIs and the connected radio link. Below are some examples showing some functions with their returned data:

- To get the status of the radio from a defined slice ID:

Function	Return data
<code>Radio_Status(Site,21438, Slice_21438_12)</code>	<code>(OK Radio_OFF Slice_OFF Radio_Slice_OFF)</code>

- To submit a KPI using a defined sliced ID related to video:

Function	Return data
<code>Slice_KPI_send(Slice_21438_12,KPI_Video, 3)</code>	(OK Failed)

- To provide access to Application KPIs and data from slice ID:

Function	Return data
<code>Slice_KPI_get(Site,21438,Slice_21438_12, Start_time,End_time)</code>	(File csv with KPIs)

The implementation code will be provided for sending and reading experiments KPIs. The following is a python script that interacts with the API:

```

1 from __future__ import print_function
2 from nac_client import NacApi
3 from xr_video_stream import XRVideoStream
4 from pprint import pprint
5 from datetime import datetime, timedelta
6
7 # Parameters:
8 server = 'http://127.0.0.1:8000'
9 username = 'user'
10 password = '123456'
11
12 # Create instance of the NaC API class:
13 api = NacApi(server, 'basic', username, password)
14
15 print('\n#### Sites:\n')
16 pprint(api.getListOfSites())
17
18 print('\n#### Site:\n')
19 pprint(api.getSite('malaga_testbed'))
20
21 print('\n#### Create new slice:\n')
22 new_slice = api.newSlice('malaga_testbed', '21438', 'slice_xr_video')
23 new_slice_id = new_slice.id
24 pprint(new_slice)
25
26 print(f'\n#### Slice ("malaga_testbed", "21438", {new_slice_id}):\n')
27 pprint(api.getSlice('malaga_testbed', '21438', new_slice_id))
28
29 # Create a extended Reality Video Session and send some video KPIs
30 if api.radioStatus('malaga_testbed', '21438', new_slice_id) is 'OK':
31     xr_session = XRVideoStream(new_slice_id)
32     video_data = xr_session.getStreamData('cam0')
33     if video_data:
34         if 'bitrate' in video_data:
35             bitrate = video_data['bitrate']
36             api.sliceKPIsend(new_slice_id, 'bitrate', 3)
37             pprint(f'KPI bitrate with value {bitrate} sent\n')
38         if 'jitter' in video_data:
39             jitter = video_data['jitter']
40             api.sliceKPIsend(new_slice_id, video_data['jitter'], 3)
41             pprint(f'KPI bitrate with value {jitter} sent\n')
42
43 # Get all KPIs from last hour
44 with open('slice_kpis.csv', 'w', newline='') as kpi_file:
45     kpi_data = api.sliceKPIget(
46         'malaga_testbed',
47         '21438',
48         new_slice_id,
49         datetime.now() - timedelta(hours=1),
50         datetime.now()
51     )
52     if kpi_data is not None:
53         kpi_file.write(csv_data)

```

6.3 API EXPOSURE REQUIREMENTS

All the components and tools of the 6G-SANDBOX facility (including those arriving through the open call), that have management, operational or service APIs that need to be exposed for the trial network orchestration or the management of the experiment, should integrate and publish their services through the Common API Framework - CAPIF.

6.3.1 WHAT IS CAPIF?

CAPIF is a standard defined by 3GPP, which aims to "apify" the network and proposes a series of standards to address and solve the harmonized and secured exposure and consumption of APIs. **CAPIF can be defined as a directory of APIs.** API specifications are stored in CAPIF as well as information to consume these APIs. In turn, CAPIF proposes solutions related to the consumption of APIs (Access control, Monitoring, Security, Events, pay per use, discovery, etc.).

6.3.2 HOW DOES CAPIF WORK?

CAPIF is made up of a series of services, with each service being responsible for a task (e.g., security, logging, monitoring, etc.). Each service is explained in depth in the services section.

CAPIF defines a set of logical entities that are the ones that operate with CAPIF and with the APIs, these entities are:

- **Invoker:** It is the equivalent of a "client" that consumes APIs. This Invoker will have to register with CAPIF, discover the APIs, and consume them.
- **Provider:** The provider can be seen as the service provider which in turn consists of three other entities:
 - **AEF** (API Exposing Function): This entity is in charge of exposing the different services that are registered in CAPIF
 - **APF** (API Publishing Function): This entity is in charge of publishing the different services
 - **AMF** (API Management Function): This entity is in charge of managing the provider (i.e., update the provider, remove provider, etc.)

The following diagram shows the CAPIF architecture.

6.3.3 EXAMPLES

To better understand the integration with CAPIF, several examples are included below:

6.3.3.1 HOW TO REGISTER A PROVIDER INTO CAPIF

The provider (AMF) must use previously provisioned credentials to obtain a token with which to onboard and obtain their ID and the certificate signed by CAPIF certification authority with which to communicate with CAPIF services.

Flow AMF to API Provider Management Service

6.3.3.2 HOW TO PUBLISH AN API INTO CAPIF

The provider (APF) should publish their services into CAPIF in order to be discoverable by invokers.

Flow APF to Publish Service

6.3.3.3 HOW TO REGISTER AN INVOKER INTO CAPIF

Just as with the provider, the invoker must use previously provisioned credentials to obtain a token with which to onboard and obtain their ID and the certificate signed by CAPIF certificate authority with which to communicate with CAPIF services.

6.3.3.4 HOW TO DISCOVER AN API VIA CAPIF

An invoker can discover published service APIs and retrieve a collection of APIs according to certain filter criteria.

Flow Invoker to Discover Service

6.3.3.5 HOW TO CONSUME AN API VIA CAPIF

Although CAPIF is not an API gateway, it can manage security aspects of API exposition (certificates or token management); however, the following steps must be completed before an invoker can consume those API.

- 1- An invoker should create a security context into CAPIF indicating which service is to be consumed.
- 2- The next step is to obtain previous security context.
- 3- The invoker can then consume the API but also the provider can verify the security context to check if the invoker is authorized (This step depends on whether tokens or certificates are being used).

6.3.4 OTHER CONSIDERATIONS

6G-SANDBOX testbeds will have a CAPIF Core Function deployed along with the 5G Core. CAPIF Core function will be available at a different URL for each testbed as shown below:

URL	PORT
capif.malaga.6g-SANDBOX.eu	443
capif.berlin.6g-SANDBOX.eu	443
capif.athens.6g-SANDBOX.eu	443
capif.oulu.6g-SANDBOX.eu	443

Providers should obtain their credentials to access CAPIF by contacting via email to malaga.testbed@6g-SANDBOX.eu

*Note: URLs and emails should be confirmed in the coming weeks.

6.3.5 CONCLUSIONS

CAPIF functionality is considered a cornerstone in the realization of 5G openness, since it allows secure exposure of 5G core APIs to third party domains. CAPIF functionality also enables third parties to define and expose their own APIs. Indeed, CAPIF has already become a fundamental feature for the 3GPP SA6, targeting the interaction of Verticals with the 5G system. More precisely, CAPIF compliance is required in the following:

- Development of Vertical Application Enablers (VAEs) for various industries (V2X, Factories of the Future, etc.)
- Realization of the Service Enabled Architecture Layer (SEAL)
- Implementation of the service side of Edge Computing services.

To go deeper into CAPIF's specifications, you can visit these links: [29222](#), [23222](#), [33122](#).

6.4 LICENSING REQUIREMENTS

Every software module to be integrated in 6G-SANDBOX platforms should be documented regarding the following points:

1. If the software requires a valid license to be used, details on how many licenses of the module are to be provided per platform, as well as information about copy protection mechanisms (e.g., USB dongle, server license, node locked license, etc.), if any. If the software module can be used by different users, information on how many users per license are supported, and details on how to generate/obtain credentials for each user.
2. Since the software may be used outside of the platforms by external experimenters accessing remotely, licensing should also address any location-related restriction.
3. If the software module depends on additional licenses produced by a third party (for example, the software module is an extension of a commercial or open-source software with a restrictive licensing model), the burden of obtaining the necessary licenses is with the proposer.

The software module provider is responsible for ensuring that IPR and licensing is properly described and handled by the proposer. In no case will the 6G-SANDBOX Project be liable due to mishandling or bad practice on the part of the proposer.

6.5 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

We envision that proposals may include hardware as part of the project. Hardware will broadly fall into two general categories: base stations (BS) (in a broad sense) and user equipment (UE), such as mobile devices, smartphones, tablets, laptops, etc.

6G-SANDBOX needs to know at submission stage about special requirements which the hardware may imply. The requirements are needed to understand the deployment implications.

In general, UE devices must be compatible with 3GPP TS 38.101, specifically in terms of operating spectrum, maximum transmitted power and receiver sensitivity.

The base station equipment should follow 3GPP TS 38.104. If the base station provides beam steering capabilities with a high gain antenna, it is expected to have an available API to ensure the ability to illuminate the 6G-SANDBOX RIS effectively.

ANNEX 1: REFERENCE CATALOGUE OF POTENTIAL EXPERIMENTS

In this section we list various potential experiments / interactions that a third party can apply in the 6G-SANDBOX facility. Each third party is requested to deliver values and ratings for application and network KPIs and quantify the added value for their target vertical sector or technology. Below we provide an indicative list of experimentation categories. This list is only to be used as an inspiration as the platforms can support probably more experiments not listed here.

- **Intelligent Applications for O-RAN.** O-RAN deployments in 6G-SANDBOX facility are available for hosting new xApps. For more information on the available O-RAN deployments please check [D3.2](#). For instance, xApps can be developed to trigger experimentation around network optimization and network monitoring or to enable new ORAN services (such as JCAS) based on off-the-shelf components.
- **Energy optimization.** 6G-SANDBOX is equipped with different energy measurements probes (AC/DC, virtual). The probes can enable experiments around energy consumption optimization via incremental technology deployment in the platforms. This can be combined with the different network topologies from 6G-SANDBOX.
- **RIS (Reflective Intelligent Surfaces).** 6G-SANDBOX has Lab and Live environment that are particularly suited to executing RIS validation experimentation. In Lab, RIS can be measured and characterized. In Live environment, the RIS deployment can be done including controlling the network to enable experimentation on network densification, network coverage extension can be realized. This can be done in FR1 as well as in FR2.
- **Network Applications utilizing Network exposure capabilities.** Focusing on the network core, NEF APIs are available in our facility, while from any domain of the network standardised exposure APIs can be provided through the CAPIF API manager. This facilitates any experiment that brings a new Network application as defined in the related [SNS white paper of the SoftNet WG](#)
- **Security.** Different tools have been deployed to allow security testing of the platforms and their application. This can be a security test such as penetration (pen) testing or fuzzing based techniques. Different attacks can be simulated to verify the robustness of applications or network components.
- **Physical layer enhancement and channel sounding.** 6G-SANDBOX can enable experimentation at the physical layer up to 140GHz. This can be done to validate state of the art component (e.g. by network analysis) or validate new PHY waveforms (including propagation). The same equipment can be used to work on channel sounding up to 140GHz.
- **Distributed MIMO.** Experimentation around the performance of distributed MIMO techniques at PHY layer is possible in the Lab. The solution enables an analysis of the benefit distributed MIMO brings to the table.
- **Digital Twin validation.** A calibrated Digital Twin has been developed which can be taken into experimentation to augment the dimension of the experiment to not just take place in the real world but to understand how the Digital twin can predict correctly the impact of the tested technology. This can be applied in many fields such as JCAS, NTN, or power optimization, to just name a few.
- **Transport Network optimizations including NTN links.** 6G-SANDBOX integrates NTN links and allows for measurements including real LEO satellites. As the first project that brings experimentation potential to NTN, we seek for use cases that integrate terrestrial and non-terrestrial links, bring radio/core functionality to the satellite, and/or utilize connect and compute resources in network infrastructures that include satellite components. 6G-SANDBOX has also a planned connectivity with ESA facility enabling the inclusion of ESA experimental capabilities.
- **KPI/KVI measurements.** The platforms enable experiment via research and measurement of new KPI or KVI by offering the wide range of tools available to execute scenarios, test and measurements. For instance, 6G-SANDBOX offers via OpenTAP automate execution of tests and scenarios, as well as collection and processing of measurements used to assess KPIs and KVIs.
- **Realistic Traffic profiling.** Research around realistic application or vertical traffic profiles can be conducted on 6G-SANDBOX. For this, connection to the Verticals is critical to ensure the environment is properly characterized on site. Once characterized, such traffic profile can be repeated in 6G-SANDBOX to perform impairment impact analysis on the KPI of the targeted vertical.
- **Zero-touch management.** 6G-SANDBOX has all the means to try out zero-touch management of trial networks. Different deployed technologies allow monitoring and automated deployment of network elements.

- **Low latency, deterministic and TSN network.** 6G-SANDBOX has deployed P4 switches allowing work around deterministic network, low latency network and time-sensitive network. The platforms have the ability to also control arbitrary packet loss, delay and jitter on selected traffic.
- **Performance Cost of Virtualization.** As outlined in D5.3, the facilities are fully characterized from a performance perspective. This means a user can define any reference trial network and compare the trial network with e.g. another (part of) technology stack. This allows the quantification of the performance cost or benefit due to the technology stack used. Example: what is my throughput if I use a certain core network in a virtual machine versus the same core deployed in a container versus a bare metal deployment.
- **Application-level Measurement campaigns.** Third parties can bring for validation their applications (from various vertical sectors). Measurements can be executed end to end with programmable traffic profiles (background and foreground). More specifically, 6G-SANDBOX is looking for use cases like those described in [FG-NET2030-Sub-G1](#) and in the scope of the [ITU IMT-2030 framework](#). Current deployed application are internet of sense and high-quality telepresence. Work is going on around industry 4.0 control systems.
- **Network-level Measurement campaigns.** 6G-SANDBOX provides a rich toolbox for network level measurements. Beyond the conventional measurements on packet and flow related KPIs (throughput, latency, error rate, goodput etc.) experiments with less examined KPIs are in scope. These include, among others, energy and security assessment of mobile network components and architectures.
- **Technology/component-specific validations.** Third parties can bring for validation their component/product and integrate it in the 6G-SANDBOX facility. Antennas, emulators, software components, end-devices etc., that realize innovative functionality are welcomed. Special interest is in Integrated Communication & Sensing (ICAS) and Joint Communication & Sensing (JCAS) solutions, as well as in devices that implement 3GPP Rel. 18 and onwards features.

ANNEX 2: KPIS PROVIDED BY THE TESTING AND VALIDATION TOOLBOX

Table 4: KPIS provided by the 6G-SANDBOX Testing and Validation Toolbox

Keysight tool	KPI family	KPI name
BreakingPoint	Capacity	TCP/HTTP Connections Per Second
BreakingPoint	Capacity	HTTP Transaction per Second
BreakingPoint	Capacity	HTTP Throughput
BreakingPoint	Capacity	Concurrent TCP/HTTP Connection Capacity
BreakingPoint	Capacity	TCP/HTTPS Connections per second
BreakingPoint	Capacity	HTTPS Transaction per Second
BreakingPoint	Capacity	HTTPS Throughput
BreakingPoint	Capacity	Concurrent TCP/HTTPS Connection Capacity
BreakingPoint	Latency	TCP/HTTP Transaction Latency
BreakingPoint	Latency	HTTPS Transaction Latency
BreakingPoint	Security	Cipher RSA 2K/4K key size – CPS performance
BreakingPoint	Security	Cipher ECDHE-RSA 256-P/512-P curve size – CPS performance
BreakingPoint	Security	Cipher ECDHE-ECDSA 256-P/512-P curve size – CPS performance
BreakingPoint	Security	Cipher TLS1_3 EC CPS Performance
BreakingPoint	Security	Block Cipher AES128/AES258 -CBC – Throughput Performance
BreakingPoint	Security	Block Cipher AES128/AES258 -GCM – Throughput Performance
BreakingPoint	Security	Block Cipher Cha-Cha-Poly – Throughput Performance
Cloud Peak	Compute	CPU cache Hit / Miss / Ratio
Cloud Peak	Compute	CPU performance score
Cloud Peak	Compute	Memory latency (ns)
Cloud Peak	Compute	Memory bandwidth (GBps)
Cloud Peak	Network	Packet loss (PPM)
Cloud Peak	Network	Packet latency (RTT)
Cloud Peak	Network	Packet latency (TCP / UDP)
Cloud Peak	Network	Packet jitter (µs)
Cloud Peak	Network	Packet TX rate (Mbps)
Cloud Peak	Network	Packet RX rate (Mbps)
Cloud Peak	Network	CPU utilization (%)
Cloud Peak	Network	Memory utilization (RAM)
Cloud Peak	Storage	BW / IOPS / Latency (read)
Cloud Peak	Storage	BW / IOPS / Latency (write)
Cloud Peak	VIM	Noisy neighbour success rate
Cloud Peak	VIM	Noisy neighbour resource usage
Cloud Peak	VIM	VM deployment success rate
Cloud Peak	VIM	VM deployment speed
CyPerf	Capacity	Total number of client and server agents in a test
CyPerf	Capacity	Throughput
CyPerf	Capacity	Connection per second
CyPerf	Capacity	Simulated users
CyPerf	Security	Total count of attacks allowed / blocked
CyPerf	Security	Total applications success / failed
CyPerf	Latency	Connect time
CyPerf	Latency	Time to first byte (TTFB)
CyPerf	Latency	Time to last byte (TTLB)
Hawkeye	Capacity	Throughput
Hawkeye	Capacity	Transactions per sec
Hawkeye	Packet Loss	Packet loss rate
Hawkeye	Packet Loss	Packet loss burst
Hawkeye	Packet Loss	Total bytes lost
Hawkeye	Latency	One way delay (ms)
Hawkeye	Latency	Jitter (ms)

Hawkeye	Latency	max jitter (ms)
Hawkeye	Latency	Max delay variation (ms)
Hawkeye	Latency	Response time (ms)
Hawkeye	Voice	Voice MOS score
Hawkeye	Video	Video MDI scores
Hawkeye	Video	Avg Video Playback Rate (bps)
Hawkeye	Video	Avg Video Pre-buffering duration (ms)
Hawkeye	Video	Video Playback Downshifts
Hawkeye	Video	Video Playback Upshifts
Hawkeye	Video	Video Quality
Hawkeye	Video	Video Stopped Count
Hawkeye	Video	Video Stopped Duration (ms)
IxLoad	Capacity	Simulated users
IxLoad	Capacity	Throughput
IxLoad	Capacity	Connections/sec
IxLoad	Capacity	Layer 7 transactions/sec
IxLoad	Capacity	Concurrent connections/sessions
IxNetwork	Frame Loss	Tx frames
IxNetwork	Frame Loss	Rx frames
IxNetwork	Frame Loss	Frame loss
IxNetwork	Frame Sequency	last sequence number
IxNetwork	Frame Sequency	duplicate frames
IxNetwork	Frame Sequency	sequence gaps
IxNetwork	Frame Sequency	reverse error
IxNetwork	Capacity	Tx frame rate
IxNetwork	Capacity	Rx frame rate
IxNetwork	Capacity	Rx rate
IxNetwork	Latency	MEF frame delay
IxNetwork	Latency	forwarding delay
IxNetwork	Latency	delay jitter
IxNetwork	Latency	inter-arrival time
IxNetwork	Capacity	Tx frame rate
IxNetwork	Capacity	Rx frame rate
IxNetwork	Capacity	Rx rate
IxNetwork	Latency	MEF frame delay
IxNetwork	Latency	forwarding delay
IxNetwork	Latency	delay jitter
IxNetwork	Latency	inter-arrival time
LoadCore	Latency	One way delay (ms)
LoadCore	Latency	delay jitter
LoadCore	Packet Loss	Packet loss

ANNEX 3: 6G-SANDBOX THIRD PARTY ENGAGEMENT REQUEST FORM

To begin a conversation with us, please use the template provided below. Copy and paste the template text and send your written responses to us by email at experimenter@6G-SANDBOX.eu.

PART 1: TELL US ABOUT YOURSELF

- Which organisation do you belong to?
- Are you active in SNS JU projects? If yes, which ones?
- Do you bring with this request an expression of interest from a specific project? If yes, which one?
- Do you require any specific confidentiality?
- Do you have a specific timeline in mind or a deadline to meet for your experiment?

PART 2: PLATFORM PREFERENCE

Please complete the table. You can visit the platforms on the website: [Athens](#), [Berlin](#), [Malaga](#), [Oulu](#)

6G-SANDBOX platform to host the experiment	Preference		If no preference to a specific platform, please indicate by 'X' the box bellow
	Primary platform Athens/ Berlin/ Malaga/ Oulu	Secondary platform Athens/ Berlin/ Malaga/ Oulu	
	Platform	Platform	
	Comment/explanation ...	Comment/explanation	
The proposed experiment can run in a platform-agnostic environment (pure virtual system)			Yes/No

PART 3: TYPE OF EXPERIMENT

Please complete the table.

Preference: Please indicate by 'X' only one of the boxes bellow		
Vertical specific experiments and KPI measurements	Technology validations and integration of third-party solutions	6G-SANDBOX facility validation and infrastructure expansion

PART 4: EXPERIMENTATION DESCRIPTION

- Briefly describe what you want to achieve with your experiment. What are the main objectives/purpose of your experiment?
- Describe the actual experimentation you want to run and, if possible, include a diagram.
- From your perspective, describe how your experiment relates to 6G?

PART 5: ETHICS CHECK

Please consider the potential ethical issues listed below as they relate to your proposal and provide further details if applicable. If there are any further potential ethical issues not specifically mentioned in the list, please be sure to mention them as well.

- Does your research involve human participants or human embryos and/or cells?
- Does your research involve animals?
- Does your research include collection and/or processing of personal data?
- Does your research include work on Artificial Intelligence?
- Do you have any relation to third countries in respect to the ethical issues mentioned above?
- Does your research harm the environment, animals, or plants?
- If there are any further potential issues, please list them below.